

COMPREHENSION SKILLS OF ELEMENTARY LEARNERS: BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNING INTERACTIVE READING ACTIVITIES (LIRA)

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 9

Pages: 956-967

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12704329

Manuscript Accepted: 06-07-2024

Comprehension Skills of Elementary Learners: Basis for Development of Learning Interactive Reading Activities (LIRA)

Cloeyline P. Dela Rosa,* Jeger P. Paragas

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study assessed the reading comprehension skills of the Grade 6 Pupils during the School Year 2022-2023. It sought to answer the following questions which involved the profile of the student-respondents in terms of age, sex, economic status, educational attainment of parents and their relationship to the parents and the teachers. Also, the reading problems encountered by the Grade 6 learners and their level of reading comprehension skills of the students based on phonetic awareness, phonics, decoding, word identification, fluency, vocabulary and comprehension. Likewise, a significant relationship between the profile of the pupils and their reading comprehension skills was also determined. The program of activities can be adopted by the teachers to improve the reading comprehension skills of Grade 6 pupils served as output of the study. Findings showed that the Grade 6 learners are younger female-dominated learners with middle socio-economic status backgrounds whose parents neither finished secondary level nor degree holder and undergraduate units with either one or both parents are working. Further, learners in the division had supervision with their parents and had regular study habit. The reading problems encountered by the Grade 6 learners are still developing with a focus on basic understanding and making meaning on fluency, vocabulary, background knowledge, comprehension strategies, lack of self-motivation, lack of background knowledge and inability to comprehend the texts were the foremost problem. Likewise, the reading comprehension ability of learners along vocabulary knowledge is developing. Further, the supervision of parents and good study habits influence the reading comprehension of learners. Additionally, these strategies could strengthen the comprehension ability of learners in school and at home. It is recommended in the study that the teachers should provide learners with specific resources or strategies aligned with their demographic background, e.g., culturally relevant texts for students from a specific background. Thus, an intervention of interactive materials shall be developed to address the concerns of Grade 6 learners in reading.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, comprehension skills, intervention, interactive materials*

Introduction

Reading is one of the basic abilities that should be learned by a child before and during schooling. This is one of the macro skills that should be honed along with listening, speaking, viewing and writing. The ability to read gives an individual a chance to understand written words and puts him at a great advantage over those who are not gifted with the ability. For learners to gain this advantage, parents need to propagate the initial seed and properly instill in their children's consciousness the importance of reading readiness. History has proven that those who love to read and who have developed a great penchant for reading easily understand the rudiments of life and its struggles because of their understanding of written words.

Moreover, reading is the foundation of academic success and life learning. One article from Philippine Star states that: "The undeniable fact remains that majority of Filipino students do not possess the ability and motivation to read. In 2007, the Department of Education reported that 70 percent of our learners are incapable of reading within the expected level. This is the situation of reading achievement intensifies in the Philippines as evaluated by Scholastic Inc., the world's largest publisher and distributor of children's book".

According to Cayubit (2012), a Filipino child needs to develop higher order skills and functional literacy. It is given that any Filipino child with sufficient reading skills would have greater chances of success in school compared to a child whose reading skills are poor and more often than not, those with poor reading skills when assessed properly are diagnosed with reading disability. Poor reading skill is manifested with poor comprehension, wrong pronunciations, among others. If no proper intervention is administered early, it could affect the academic, social and psychological development of the child. As such, proper and correct diagnosis of reading disability as early as possible appears to be essential.

Due to the fast evolving world and changing technology it cannot be denied that sometimes reading is taken for granted. Former DepEd Sec. Abad deplored the poor performance of the pupils' assessment test and said that, the low scores in English, Mathematics and Science can be attributed to pupils' lack of ability in basic reading and comprehension. In addition, he said that one of the major problems in reading is the poor reading comprehension, which leads to poor understanding of printed symbols.

However, there are children who have difficulties in decoding and recognizing words. It has been noted that students who struggle with decoding rarely have a chance to interact with more difficult text and often learn to dislike reading. This further challenge the reader who often lose interest or completely quit learning. More likely than not, those around them become affected.

Generally, due to the net lingo and shortcut text words that were emerging, students in the Philippines now find it hard to read and

understand materials written in Filipino. Studies conducted on this issue reveal that children's familiarity with the language used at home has a great impact on the results of the studies. From there, the level of knowledge of the spoken words could be raised until such time that the students can fully comprehend what has been read and be able to integrate that knowledge into the daily life. Though it will take time to improve the knowledge of cognitive and metacognitive strategies, their reasoning abilities, motivation and level of engagement, instilling in the students the love for reading will prepare them to face and accept the reality that an above standard of reading and comprehend will also improve their total personality by developing self-confidence and nurturing that hidden strength to overcome the challenges of communication.

With these problems, the Department of Education (DepEd) intensifies reading literacy in schools by enforcing the program called "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP). The undersecretary said that the new program aims to make every Filipino a reader at the end of Grade III. The undersecretary is expecting that no pupil will be promoted to higher grades unless he/she manifests mastery and basic literacy skills in particular grade.

In January 2013, USAID/Philippines launched Basa Pilipinas (Read Philippines), its flagship basic education activity to support the Philippines' goal of improving the reading skills of one million early grade students by training teachers and school heads on effective reading instruction, producing curriculum-based teaching and learning materials (TLMs) for use in early grade classrooms and strengthening the capacity of the Department of Education (DepEd) to effectively implement the language and literacy component of its K-12 curriculum reforms. The USAID/Philippines, through its Basa Pilipinas program has reached over 1.8 million students from Kindergarten to Grade 3, trained over 19,000 teachers and school heads and provided over 10 million units of TLMs to 3,000 public elementary schools in the Philippines. After five years of Basa Implementation, reading assessments have shown notable improvements in students' reading skills, particularly in Filipino, the national language and one of the official languages of instruction throughout the K-12 cycle.

But despite these actions, the Philippines became the lowest in reading comprehension as a worldwide study in 2018 revealed that the Philippines scored the lowest in reading comprehension. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) is a worldwide study by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development. They examine student's capabilities in reading, mathematics, and science. In the study, there were 79 countries that participated. Among those 79, the Philippines scored the lowest in reading comprehension. The study was conducted back in 2018. Reading was the main subject that was assessed among 15-year-old students. The Philippines scored an average of 340 in reading. The score was over 200 points below China who had 555. It was also 100 points lower than the OECD average of 487. Both boys and girls ranked lowest among PISA participating countries.

In regard to the above- cited scenario, this study sought answers to the apprehensions of Grade 7 students over reading comprehension in Filipino reading materials. With this, the researcher hoped to establish the parameters of the difficulties and come up with solutions that will call on the involvement of parents, teachers and the students on how to improve the reading comprehension skills of the students. Since the concern of the Department of Education is to produce competitive readers among the pupils and make them fully understand what they have read, interventions were introduced to attain the objectives of the department with respect to the reading comprehension skills and problems of the pupils. Likewise, the researcher was motivated by the need to address the growing concern among teachers that pupils are mono-syllabic readers in English but comprehends better when presented with texts written in the native vernacular.

Research Questions

This study assessed the reading comprehension level of the Grade 6 Pupils during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. economic status
 - 1.4. educational attainment of farther;
 - 1.5. educational attainment of mother;
 - 1.6. academic guidance from parents; and
 - 1.7. study habits?
2. What are the reading problems encountered by the Grade 6 students?
3. How may the reading comprehension skills of the students be described based on:
 - 3.1. phonetic awareness;
 - 3.2. phonics;
 - 3.3. decoding;
 - 3.4. word identification;
 - 3.5. fluency;
 - 3.6. vocabulary and
 - 3.7. comprehension?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the pupils and their reading comprehension skills?
5. What program of activities can be adopted by the teachers to improve the reading comprehension skills of Grade 6 pupils?

Methodology

Research Design

This research study utilized the descriptive-survey method of research. A descriptive survey uses surveys to gather data about varying subjects. This data aims to know the extent to which different conditions can be obtained among these subjects.

Calmorin (2007) pointed out that descriptive researches are purposive processes of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, process, trends, and cause-effect relationships about such data with or without the aid of statistical tools. Calmorin (2007) further claimed that survey signifies the gathering of data regarding present conditions through the use of questionnaire. Descriptive studies describe phenomena associated with a subject population or to samples of that population that have certain common characteristics (Cooper, Hedges, & Valentine, 2009).

According to Best (2006) as cited by Arcaina (2010), descriptive research includes all studies that purpose to presents facts concerning nature and status of anything a group of persons, number of objects, a set of conditions, a class of events or any kind of phenomena one may wish to study. In addition, descriptive research can be distinguished from the other forms of research on the basis of the following characteristics: 1) Descriptive research is non-experimental in that it deals with relationships between non-manipulated variables in a natural rather than artificial setting. 2) Descriptive research involves hypothesis formulation and testing. 3) the descriptive research uses logical methods of inductive and deductive reasoning in order to arrive at generalizations. 4) all of the variables and procedures used in descriptive studies are described as completely and accurately as possible so as to permit future replication. 5) Descriptive research often employs methods of randomization so that error can be estimated when inferring population characteristics from observations of samples.

Participants

The respondents of the study was the public elementary pupils. The pupils were from the respective districts of elementary schools of Schools Division of Aurora.

The researcher employed the complete enumeration technique a type of purposive sampling technique for entire members of the population (total population) that have a particular set of characteristics like specific attributes/traits, experience, knowledge, skills, and exposure to an event or phenomena procedure. Additionally, total enumeration was employed by the researcher to give all the members of the population had the opportunities and equal chances.

The table below shows the total number of Grade 6 pupils of public elementary schools in the Municipality of Baler, Aurora.

<i>Public Elementary Schools in the Municipality of Baler</i>		
<i>Name of School</i>	<i>School Classification</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
1. A.V Mijares ES	EO 189	1
2. Baler Central School	Mother School	2
3. Calabuanan ES	EO 189	10
4. Carmen T. Valenzuela IS	EO 189	1
5. Diego Ortiz	EO 189	1
6. Ruperto Zubia ES	EO 189	1
7. Mariano L. Sindac ES	EO 189	4
8. Setan ES	EO 189	4
9. Suklayin ES	EO 189	2
Total no. of Respondents		63

Instruments

A locally constructed questionnaire served as the source of data for the study. The questionnaire had three (3) parts. The first part contains the description of the profile of the student-respondents in terms of age, sex, economic status, educational attainment of parents and their relationship to the parents and the teachers. The second part is about the reading problems encountered by the Grade 6 learners. The third part is on the reading comprehension skills of the students based on phonetic awareness, phonics, decoding, word identification, fluency, vocabulary and comprehension. Part II and Part III of the questionnaire items have a Filipino translation to facilitate honest response of the respondents.

According to Zulueta (2010), questionnaires such as research instrument, require the respondents to neither write answers to questions about the topic or answer orally. The answer form is usually structures. There are fixed choices or the form may be open. The respondents can create their own words. The key word in questionnaire construction is relevance which has three facets: relevance of the study's goal, relevance of questions to the goals of the study and relevance of the question to the questions to the individual.

Finally, all the data gathered using different parts of the instrument were collected, tabulated, analysed, and interpreted.

The research instrument prepared by the researcher was subjected to content validation. There were three (3) experts or validators from the institution wherein the researcher is affiliated with. Evaluators must be graduates of any relevant post-graduate studies in their field of specialization; and have had the mastery and knowledge enough in writing academic work, particularly in evaluating such research instruments.

The results of the content validation of the instrument was reflected in the Appendix along with its numerical and verbal interpretation. The questionnaire was evaluated using the five-point scale questionnaire. The evaluators used the Content Validation Instrument by Meimban and Meimban, (2021). Their comments and suggestions were incorporated, served, and manifested.

Furthermore, the content validity of the questionnaire was described in terms of the following scale values with the corresponding descriptive equivalence:

Weighted Mean Scale	Descriptive Rating
4.50- 5.00	Highly Valid
3.50- 4.49	Valid
2.50- 3.49	Moderately Valid
1.50- 2.49	Fairly Valid
1.00- 1.49	Not Valid

The average ratings of the evaluators was computed to determine the content validity with corresponding descriptive equivalence to ensure the truthfulness of data and credibility of anticipated results.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission of the Schools Division Superintendent and the Principal prior to the conduct of the study. The instrument was applied after a thorough consultation with three (3) Master Teachers after establishing its reliability and validity.

Respondents with problems in reading was further subjected to the instruments of the study. Parts I and III were administered to students to determine the reading skills of those with identified problems in reading. With the researcher personally handling the administration of the survey questionnaires through interview method, a one hundred percent (100%) retrieval rate was achieved.

Data-gathering commenced when the researchers already secured the approval of the Office of the School Division Superintendent had received and all the school heads were informed about the study and the data-gathering activity.

The researcher oriented the respondents about the study and request them to answer all items in the questionnaire as honestly and as accurately as possible. The researcher answered any queries for clarification from the respondents.

Once everything is settled, the survey questionnaires was administered systematically to all respondents. The questionnaires was retrieved by the researcher and data was organized, coded, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

To come up with valid and reliable results, the appropriate statistical tools were employed. Further, in rejecting and accepting the hypothesis, the researchers obtained a set of 0.05 level of significance to determine the association of the results.

For problem number 1, the researcher utilized frequency counts and percentage distribution on the profile of the respondents.

To answer problem No. 2, data gathered was collated and tabulated. Using appropriate tables, the data was presented. The following statistical tools was applied in the analysis and interpretation of data.

The grand mean was computed in determining the profiles of the respondents. The computed mean and standard deviation was used to test strength of the reading problems experienced by the respondents. The relationship of the significance of the relationship of the variables, is tested using correlational analysis using Point-biserial and Spearman Rank Correlation. These non-parametric measures test the validity of the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the Grade VI learners and their reading comprehension skills.

Further, the research instrument was subjected to content validation using the five-point scale questionnaire. Evaluator's comments and suggestions were incorporated and served as bases in the modification of the instrument.

Further, the average ratings of the evaluators were computed to determine the content validity with corresponding transmuted ratings to ensure the usefulness and validity of the information to be gathered. In this study, it was found out that the questionnaire is highly valid with a value of 4.94 which implies that the instrument was described as highly valid that covered all the areas needed in the study.

In addition, the questionnaire was subjected to the reliability test in which the questionnaire will be administered to a sample of 30 respondents in the municipality. In addition, the questionnaire subjected to the reliability test in which the questionnaire was

administered to a sample of 30 respondents in the districts. Such tests were used to measure the consistency of the test administered.

Reliability Test

The table below shows the data on reliability analysis on the questionnaire.

Table 1. *Reliability Analysis of the Data Gathering Instrument*

<i>Part</i>	<i>Cronbach coefficient</i>
Reading Problem Encountered	0.989
Reading Comprehension Skills	0.986
Overall	0.988

Cronbach's alpha measures the reliability, or internal consistency of the instrument. The computed Cronbach's alpha values for the Level of Digital Leadership Competency and Current Challenges Encountered are 0.989 and 0.986, respectively with an overall value of 0.988. The Cronbach coefficient is above the 0.7 threshold which suggests that the instrument provides an excellent internal consistency.

Ethical Considerations

The data collected was solely for the purpose of the study. The researcher ensured the confidentiality of their responses. All information provided by the respondents was held STRICTLY CONFIDENTIAL.

Further, proper citations were observed as an academic way of acknowledging and giving credit to the contributions of other researchers and writers. Intellectual honesty must be always practiced by the researcher.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion of the conducted study. The data presentation was done through tabulation that shows the frequency, percentage distribution, and other statistical treatments used to interpret the data. Tabulated and statistically treated data were the bases of the analysis and interpretation of this study.

Profile of the Grade 6 Pupils

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents which involved the demographic and academic profiles such as age, sex, economic status, educational attainment of parents, study guidance from parents, and study habits, respectively.

Table 2. Profile of the Grade 6 Pupils n=63

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>		
Age	11	16	25.4		
	12	47	74.6		
Sex	Male	29	46.0		
	Female	34	54.0		
Economic Status	Family can afford some perks	20	31.7		
	Only one of the parents is working	26	41.3		
	Both parents have stable job	17	27.0		
Educational Attainment	Mother	Secondary	16	25.4	
		Undergraduate units	14	22.2	
		Bachelor's degree	15	23.8	
	Father	Bachelor's degree with graduate units	11	17.5	
		Master of Arts or Master of Science with post graduate units	7	11.1	
		Secondary	7	11.1	
		Undergraduate units	17	27.0	
Study Guidance from Parents	Mother	Bachelor's degree	11	17.5	
		Bachelor's degree with graduate units	12	19.0	
		Master of Arts or Master of Science with post graduate units	16	25.4	
	Father	Studies with supervision of parents	49	77.8	
		Studies without supervision of parents	14	22.2	
		Study Habits	Has study habit once a week	13	20.6
			Has study habit every other day	16	25.4
Has regular study habit	34		54.0		

Age. Table 2 shows that the majority of the Grade 6 learners belong to age 12 with that constitutes 47 or 74.6 percent whereas 16 or 25.4 percent belong to age 11. The student reading profile as to age implies that the age of the respondents falls in the category of Grade 7 learners with ages 11-12 as to the current educational system under K to 12 implementation process.

Sex. As to sex, more than half of the learners are female that constitute 34 or 54 percent whereas 29 or 46 percent are males. Data implies that the learners are female dominated. Gonzalez (2008) as cited by Velasquez (2014) pointed out that in Philippine culture, girls obtain better grades than boys not because girls are inherently superior, but because they are more diligent and have better study habits.

Economic Status. The socio-economic status of learners obtained 26 or 41.3 percent indicated that only one of the parents is working; learners who have family can afford some perks with a frequency of 20 that constitutes 31.7 percent; and 17 or 27 percent have both parents have stable job. Data implies that learners had parents either working or not working. Further, parental socioeconomic status (SES), generally indicated by household income and parental education, impacts children's literacy skills as cited by Gonzalez et al., 2017. It is observed that SES is not only linked to children's language skills but also to the type of parental speech addressed to a child at home. The study of Rowe et al., (2012) show that parents with a higher SES use more words, a richer vocabulary and some grammatically more complex utterances when interacting with their children than parents with a low SES.

Parents' Educational Attainment. As to the learners' parents' educational attainment, one-fourth of the learners' mother graduated in secondary level whereas less than one-fourth of learners' mothers earned bachelor's degree with 15 or 23.8 percent. Also, the learners' mothers earned undergraduate units that constitute 14 or 22.2. As to fathers' educational attainment, data indicate that 17 or 27 percent had undergraduate units whereas 16 or 25.4 percent earned Master of Arts or Master of Science with post graduate units. Data corroborates the findings on the economic status of parents that validates the parents' educational attainment of learners. Data implies that the parents of the respondents either finished high school level, earned 4 year-degree course, and had undergraduate units.

In the literature of Zheng and Libertus (2018) suggest that parents' education and household income play different roles in determining parents' beliefs about the importance of the school and parenting behavior at home in teaching math or reading/writing to their child. Also, as affirmed by Froiland et.al (2014), parents who have a high education level provide a family environment enriched in literacy, have more positive attitudes toward shared reading and therefore have a positive influence on the development of their children's language and literacy skills.

Study Guidance from Parents. More than half of the respondents had supervision with their parents with 49 or 77.8 percent whereas 14 or 22.2 percent are learners with no supervision of their parents. Data indicates that even the respondents' parents are working or not working, they had their time to supervise the studies of their children. It is pointed out by Ecalte et.al (2023) that the aspects of family literacy such as parental reading habits, the number of books in a household, parental involvement in their children's literacy activities, parental attitudes toward shared reading, parents' literacy-related attitudes are positive and reinforcement activities of home literacy environment that establish a home-school partnership toward literacy instruction.

Study Habits. The study habits of learners described the recurrent, unconscious pattern of behavior that is acquired through repetition. This described the desirability of the students in acquiring knowledge by doing schoolworks and assignments, specifically along the different rudiments of reading. Data shows that more than half of the respondents (34 or 54 percent) had regular study habit; others had study habit every other day with 16 or 25.4 percent; and had study habit once a week with 13 or 20.6 percent. It can be inferred that the respondents had good study habits. In view of learning, attitudes of learners toward good study habits indicated that learners facilitate further learning and this contains them the course of further motivation in their studies.

The findings of the study negates the studies of Jafari, H., A. Aghaei; and A. Khatony (2019) revealed that the status of study habits was at moderate level for most students. It is recommended in the study to consider and assess students' study habits at the time of entry into university, in addition, specific training should be offered to students in order to help them learn or modify study habits to increase their academic achievements. Generally, it is therefore important to identify the backgrounds and reading profiles of the students in order to tailor fit interventions to meet their reading needs.

As pointed out by Bustos and Espiritu (1990) as cited by Velasquez (2012), there are specific factors influencing differences among learners. These factors are age, sex, and family and community backgrounds. As explained in the various developmental theories, age represents the learner's level of maturity and hence, his possible educability. On the other hand, the sex differences have certain biological factors like anatomical, physical, and physiological differences between boys and girls which may lead to psychological differences.

Furthermore, studies in psychology have shown that there exist wide variations among members of different families. These variations can be attributed to environmental influence. Poor home background, lack of nutrition, low economic status, and low cultural level affect the readiness of an individual to learn. The learning experiences in which a child engages or has engaged in his home or neighborhood environment influence his interest, his attitude toward school, and his acquired study- all of which contribute factors of difference among learners.

Reading Problems Encountered by the Respondents

Table 3 presents the reading problems encountered by the respondents in reading comprehension along with the level of challenges they encountered.

Table 3. *Reading Problems Encountered by the Grade 6 Students*

	<i>Reading Comprehension Problems</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I always look up the meanings of unknown words in my dictionary every time I have problems with difficult vocabulary.	3.57	Often Happens
2.	When I read, I read aloud to help me remember well.	3.76	Often Happens
3.	When I read, I cannot predict what will come next.	3.30	Sometimes Happens
4.	I don't like reading books even reading in my native language.	3.98	Often Happens
5.	I think the reading problems come from the instructions and materials which affect my interest in reading.	3.95	Often Happens
6.	When the text is too difficult, boring and uninteresting. I fail to read.	3.83	Often Happens
7.	When I have no interest in the topic discussed in a reading material. I find it even more difficult.	4.19	Often Happens
8.	I don't know the vocabulary and idiomatic usage so I cannot understand what I'm reading.	3.78	Often Happens
9.	I don't know sentence structures so I cannot understand what I'm reading.	4.10	Often Happens
10.	I cannot sequence and connect ideas in reading text because I don't know the text organization.	4.16	Often Happens
11.	My weak grammar causes misinterpretation of the reading text.	4.08	Often Happens
12.	I'm not quite sure whether I know the meanings of some difficult words.	3.86	Often Happens
13.	I often have problems with technical terms when I read the academic articles or texts.	4.06	Often Happens
14.	I must read every single word: otherwise, I'm afraid I might miss the important point which will affect my comprehension of the whole texts.	3.76	Often Happens
15.	When I read a passage. I tend to connect its content with my own previous knowledge related to the topic, and this is sometimes different from what the author intended in the passage.	3.89	Often Happens
16.	Some culture-loaded words and phrases will mislead my comprehension of a reading material.	4.32	Often Happens
17.	Sometimes even if I know every word in a passage. I still find difficulty in understanding the whole passage and grasping its central idea because of my limited background knowledge.	3.94	Often Happens
18.	I thought that I understood the passage quite well, but it turned out that I gave wrong answers to several comprehension questions after it.	3.90	Often Happens
19.	I cannot concentrate till the end of a passage. When reading a long and boring passage. I often forget the former part when I read the latter part.	3.94	Often Happens
20.	After reading a passage once, I seem to forget what I have already read, and have to move backward and reread it.	3.92	Often Happens
	Overall Mean	3.91	Often Happens

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never Happens); 1.50-2.49 (Seldom Happens); 2.50-3.49 (Sometimes Happens); 3.50-4.49 (Often Happens); 4.50-5.00 (Always Happens)

Data indicate the overall weighted mean value of 3.91 which described as often happens which implies that the problems they encountered happened much of the time, Among the indicators that often happens were indicators that described the following items: (1) Some culture-loaded words and phrases will mislead my comprehension of a reading material (4.32); (2) When I have no interest in the topic discussed in a reading material. I find it even more difficult (4.19); (3) I cannot sequence and connect ideas in reading text because I don't know the text organization (4.16); (4) I don't know sentence structures so I cannot understand what I'm reading (4.10); (5) My weak grammar causes misinterpretation of the reading text (4.08); and (6) I often have problems with technical terms when I read the academic articles or texts (4.06). Data implies that the respondents experienced challenges on cultural concept words, motivation in reading, text organization, sentence structures, grammar issues, and too technical terms in the text. Data suggest the technical and behavioral aspect of learners in reading comprehension.

This finding supports the study conducted by Virtucio (2019) where her findings revealed that majority of Grade 7 students obtained low performance in reading comprehension problems along fluency, vocabulary, background knowledge, comprehension strategies, lack of self-motivation, lack of background knowledge and inability to comprehend the texts were the foremost problem encountered by Grade 7 students affecting the performance of the respondents in reading.

On the other hand, Adduru (2009) as cited by Velasquez (2012) in his article stressed the following factors affecting the level of achievement of a child: (1) teacher- factor which has a great influence on the achievement level of students; (2) the home, which is considered the foundation of a child; poverty which constitutes lack of learning materials like magazines, books, newspapers, etc. deprives the child from learning more; the school's physical facilities, administration support and the curriculum.

Reading Comprehension Skill of the Respondents

Table 4 presents the reading comprehension skills of the respondents presents the data that described along phonemic awareness, phonics, decoding, word identification, fluency, vocabulary and communication.

Table 4. *Reading Comprehension Skills of the Students*

<i>Reading Comprehension Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
PHONEMIC AWARENESS		
Counting the syllables of the word helps me picture out its meaning.	4.02	Often Happens
Appreciating the rhyme and alliteration of the words in each sentence helps me picture out its meaning.	3.83	Often Happens
Invents the spelling of the words when it can't be spelled correctly.	4.22	Often Happens
Mean	4.02	Often Happens
PHONICS		
Knows how to read and speak the consonants.	3.89	Often Happens
Knows the difference between the sounds of long and short vowels.	3.71	Often Happens
Aware of the different English vowels. (A,E,I,O,U, Y)	3.97	Often Happens
Mean	3.86	Often Happens
DECODING		
Tries to interpret the writer's intention while reading English text.	3.94	Often Happens
Predicts the main idea of the whole passage from the key words.	4.13	Often Happens
Determines unknown words based on their background knowledge on the topic of the story.	4.02	Often Happens
Mean	4.03	Often Happens
WORD IDENTIFICATION		
Asks to read from a list of words.	4.11	Often Happens
Identifies words with remarkable speed and accuracy.	3.94	Often Happens
Practices to identify meanings and say the unknown words daily.	3.95	Often Happens
Mean	4.00	Often Happens
FLUENCY		
Understand and recognizes words automatically.	3.92	Often Happens
Reads a text accurately, quickly and with expression.	3.95	Often Happens
Understands complicated materials through quickly reading the first and the last paragraphs.	3.94	Often Happens
Mean	3.94	Often Happens
VOCABULARY		
Bothers with the grammatical structure of English sentences while reading	4.03	Often Happens
Guesses the meaning of new words by analyzing its roots, prefixes or suffixes.	4.16	Often Happens
Skips words that are new.	4.06	Often Happens
Mean	4.08	Often Happens
COMMUNICATION		
Asks questions before, during and after reading.	4.22	Often Happens
Distinguishes between minor and major points.	4.17	Often Happens
Summarizes a passage.	4.05	Often Happens
Mean	4.15	Often Happens
Overall Mean	4.01	Often Happens

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never Happens); 1.50-2.49 (Seldom Happens); 2.50-3.49 (Sometimes Happens); 3.50-4.49 (Often Happens); 4.50-5.00 (Always Happens)

Data indicates the overall weighted mean value of 4.01 which described as often happens. This implies that all statements showed the comprehension skills of the respondents as they were much encountered most of the time as along phonemic awareness, phonics, decoding, word identification, fluency, and communication. However, along aspect of vocabulary, the respondents often times encountered grammatical structure of English sentences while reading, guessing meaning of new words by analyzing its roots, prefixes or suffixes; and skipping words that are new. Also, data entails that reading comprehension skills along vocabulary building skill need remediation activities or enhancement.

Results of this study corroborate the study conducted by Boakye (2017) revealed that a number of students have little reading experience, use inappropriate reading strategies, and have low self-efficacy and poor reading habits. In addition, students identified comprehension, language, vocabulary, length and density of Sociology texts as factors compounding their reading challenges.

Relationship Between the Profile of the Pupils and their Reading Comprehension Skills

The table presents the relationship between the profile of the Grade 6 learners and their reading comprehension skills.

Table 5 shows the test of relationship between the profile of the pupils and their reading comprehension skills using Point – Biserial and Spearman – rank correlation. These coefficients were inferentially tested to determine if the computed coefficients are significantly different from zero. Results revealed that reading comprehension skills is significantly associated with the study habits and study

guidance from parents. The results suggest that pupils with a high level of reading comprehension skills are those that are supervised by their parents and have regular study habits. Data implies that parents' supervision and good study habits are indicators to improve the reading comprehension skills of learners.

Table 5. Relationship Between the Profile of the Pupils and their Reading Comprehension Skills

Profile	Reading Comprehension Skills														Overall Mean	
	Phonetic Awareness		Phonics		Decoding		Word Identification		Fluency		Vocabulary		Comprehension			
	r	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.
Age	-0.018	0.886	-0.068	0.598	0.004	0.973	-0.031	0.808	-0.019	0.882	-0.030	0.812	-0.029	0.822	-0.026	0.837
Sex	-0.003	0.984	-0.092	0.475	0.032	0.802	0.000	1.000	0.023	0.855	-0.009	0.946	-0.015	0.908	-0.006	0.965
Economic Status	0.063	0.621	0.070	0.588	0.030	0.815	0.016	0.903	0.039	0.761	0.047	0.713	0.034	0.790	0.047	0.715
Educational Attainment																
Mother	0.048	0.707	0.085	0.509	0.009	0.944	-0.008	0.951	0.025	0.848	0.020	0.878	0.003	0.979	0.037	0.775
Father	0.103	0.420	0.130	0.310	0.065	0.613	0.049	0.706	0.087	0.497	0.078	0.544	0.042	0.747	0.081	0.527
Study Guidance from Parents	-.745**	0.000	-.769**	0.000	-.723**	0.000	-.686**	0.000	-.748**	0.000	-.751**	0.000	-.757**	0.000	-.759**	0.000
Study Habits	.602**	0.000	.608**	0.000	.577**	0.000	.602**	0.000	.591**	0.000	.577**	0.000	.584**	0.000	.632**	0.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Moreover, these findings can inform educational practices and parental involvement strategies to support children's reading development. With good study habits and parental supervision linked to improved reading comprehension, schools and educators can provide resources and workshops to help parents effectively supervise their children's reading activities.

The study conducted by Iheakanwa (2021) indicates that a significant relationship exists between reading ability and students' performance, study habit and student's performance. Also, there is no significant statistical relationship exist between sex and students' performance. It is recommended in the study that students' reading interest be strengthened by providing and equipping school libraries; reading should be given adequate attention in classroom activity and not left to students' choice or discretion.

Meanwhile, a study titled Perceptions of Teachers about the Role of Parents in Developing Reading Habits of Children to Improve their Academic Performance in Schools (ERIC) by Umaima et al. (2018) [2] explores the teachers' perspective on parental involvement in developing reading habits. This study emphasizes the teacher's belief that parental support in creating reading routines and encouraging reading for pleasure can enhance academic performance, including reading comprehension.

Escalona (2012) stated that assessing the student's attitude towards reading provides a good basis for teachers in developing useful educational interventions to facilitate learning. She also stressed that knowing how the student's feel toward their teachers, their teaching strategies, classroom activities, and the subject matter plays a great role in student's performance.

According to Duladol (as cited by Velasquez 2012), study habits among learners are things to be given emphasis and consideration by educators during early stages while the minds of children are still fresh and pliable. Pupils who have developed good study habits are likely manifest them in their performance. Ergo, valuing good study habits is the key to effective learning.

Singh (2011) as cited by Velasquez (2012) studied "A Survey of the Study Habits of High, Middle and Low Achiever Adolescents in Relation to Their Sex, Intelligence and Socio-economic status". A sample of 1600 adolescent students (800 boys and 800 girls) studying in class IX was selected randomly from high and higher secondary schools of rural and urban areas of Himachal Pradesh. Analysis of the data was carried out by applying analysis of variance.

The main findings of the study were: (1) adolescent boys had significantly better study habits than adolescent girls; (2) study habits were related to the academic achievement significantly; (3) high achieving adolescents had significantly better study habits than middle achievers and middle achievers had significantly better study habits than low achievers; (4) study habits of adolescent boys and adolescent girls differed significantly at different levels of academic achievement i.e., high, middle and low; (5) study habits of adolescent boys and adolescent girls differed significantly at different levels of intelligence i.e. high, middle and low; (6) academic achievement and socioeconomic status interacted significantly in relation to the study habits of adolescent boys and girls; and (7) the triple interaction among academic achievement, intelligence and socioeconomic status was not significant in relation to the study habits of either adolescent boys or girls.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing significant findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The Grade 6 learners are younger female-dominated learners with middle socio-economic status backgrounds whose parents neither finished secondary level nor degree holder and undergraduate units with either one or both parents are working. Further, learners in the division had supervision with their parents and had regular study habit.

2. The reading problems encountered by the Grade 6 learners are still developing with a focus on basic understanding and making meaning on fluency, vocabulary, background knowledge, comprehension strategies, lack of self-motivation, lack of background knowledge and inability to comprehend the texts were the foremost problem.

3. The reading comprehension ability of learners along vocabulary knowledge is developing. Learners can better understand new information when they have some prior knowledge and vocabulary knowledge of the topic.

4. The supervision of parents and good study habits influence the reading comprehension of learners. Further, these strategies could strengthen the comprehension ability of learners in school and at home.

In the light of the significant findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are offered:

The teachers shall provide learners with specific resources or strategies aligned with their demographic background, e.g., culturally relevant texts for students from a specific background. 2. The school leaders in collaboration with the community stakeholders shall support learners by offering specific programs or interventions that address potential challenges due to social economic status such as after-school reading clubs with small group instruction and other school interventions to cater the reading problems they encountered.

The teachers shall address the specific weakness in reading comprehension such as vocabulary development through specific strategies or materials in improving the reading comprehension skills. An intervention interactive materials shall be developed to address the concerns of Grade 6 learners.

The schools shall intensify the home-school collaboration for parents/guardians to support reading comprehension at home and sustain good study habits. Also, teachers shall consider varied ways to create a print-rich environment or discuss reading strategies for the identified learners.

Future research shall explore different types of parental supervision and their specific effects on reading comprehension. Additionally, longitudinal studies could track the development of reading comprehension skills over time in relation to parental involvement and study habits.

References

- Al Khateeb, O. (2010). The Impact of Using KWL Strategy on Grade Ten Female Students' Reading Comprehension of Religious Concepts in Ma'an City. Retrieved August 10, 2010 from World Wide Web http://www.eurojournals.com/ejss_12_3_14.pdf.
- Bilbao, M., Donguilla, C., & Vasay, M. (2016). Level of reading comprehension of the education students. *International Journal of Liberal Arts, Education, Social Sciences and Philosophical Studies*, 4(1), 342-353. Retrieved February 26, 2018, from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=13762>
- Billah, M. (2015, July 1). Significance of Silent Reading. *The Daily Observer*. Retrieved from <http://www.observerbd.com>
- Blay, R., Mercado, K., & Villacorta, J. (2009). The relationship between motivation and second language reading comprehension among fourth grade Filipino students. *Philippine ESL Journal* vol. 2, Feb. 2009
- Boakye, N. (2017). Exploring Students' Reading Profiles to Guide a Reading Intervention Programme.
- Cabardo, Jimmy Rey O., (2015). Reading Proficiency Level of Students: Basis for Reading Intervention Program. DepED – Hagonoy National High School. Retrieved on 13 June 2018.
- Cayubit RFO (2012). Vocabulary and reading comprehension as a measure of reading skills of Filipino children. Unpublished Thesis: University of Santo Tomas. Downloaded at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282121510>.
- Celestino, J. C. (2014). Reading difficulties of freshmen students in the college of information technology and computing science. *QSU Research Journal*, 3(1), 1-7. Retrieved
- Davis, Allison, (2011). *Building Comprehension Strategies*. Australia. Retrieved on 25 June 2018.
- DepEd Order No.47, s. 2017 amendment to DepEd Order No. 18, s. 2017 re: Guidelines on the Utilization of the Every a Reader Program (ECARP).
- Duke, N. & Pearson, D. (2002). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension. In *What research has to say about reading instruction* (3rd ed., pp. 205-210). International Reading Association.
- Ecalte, J. et.al. (2023). Profiles of learner readers and their early literacy skills and environmental predictors: a large-scale longitudinal study from preschool to grade 1. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2023.1189046/full>
- Fidler, R., (2009). *The Reading Comprehension Skills of Students with Dyslexia*. Retrieved on 13 June 2018.
- Franza, M. (2018). Personal attributes and reading competence of grade nine students. "Tin-aw" Graduate School Book of Abstracts, 2(1), 1-9. Retrieved January 22, 2019, from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=13626>

- Froiland, J. M., Powell, D. R., and Diamond, K. E. (2014). Relations among neighborhood social networks, home literacy environments, and children's expressive vocabulary in suburban at-risk families. *Sch. Psychol. Int.* 35, 429–444. doi: 10.1177/0143034313500415
- Gonzalez, J. E., Acosta, S., Davis, H., Pollard-Durodola, S., Saenz, L., Soares, D., et al. (2017). Latino maternal literacy beliefs and practices mediating socioeconomic status and maternal education effects in predicting child receptive vocabulary. *Early Educ. Dev.* 28, 78–95. doi: 10.1080/10409289.2016.1185885
- Hale, A. et al. (2011). Reading assessment methods for middle-school students: An investigation of reading comprehension rate and maze accurate response rate. *Psychology in the Schools*, 48(1), 28-36.
- Hallorina, G. T. (2009). The effectiveness of Instrumental religious music on selected reading comprehension skills and reading comprehension level of first year college students. *HCDC Faculty Research Journal*, 11(1), 1-17. Retrieved January 5, 2019, from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=593>
- Hartney, R. N. (2011). Investigating Reading Difficulties in English Second Language of Grade 3 Learner in one Primary School in the Khomas Education Region of Namibia. Windhoek: UNAM.
- Hellekjaer, Glenn Ole, (2009). Academic English Reading Proficiency on the University Level: A Norwegian Case Study.
- Iheakanwa, J. et al. (2021). Reading Ability, Study Habits and Students' Academic Performance in Social Studies
- Imam, Ombra A., et al., (2013). Reading Comprehension Skills and Performance in Science Among High School Students in the Philippines. *Datu Siang National High School, Cotabato City*. Retrieved on 13 June 2018.
- Jafari, H., Aghaei, A., and Khatony (2019) Relationship between study habits and academic achievement in students of medical sciences in Kermanshah-Iran.
- Jaśim, B. (2007). The impact of instruction in critical reading strategies on advanced Iraqi EFL learners' comprehension. *College of Basic Education Researchers Journal*, 7(1), 320-363.
- Kaplan, S., & Saccuzzo, D. (2009). *Psychological testing: Principles, applications and Issues* (7th ed.). Belmont CA: Thomson Wadsworth
- Khabiri, M., & Pakzad, M. (2012). The effect of teaching critical reading strategies on EFL learners' vocabulary retention. *The Journal of Teaching Language Skills (JTLS)*, 4(1).
- Lastrella, S. (2010). Reading difficulties of first year students in the university of Makati S.Y. 2010-2011. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Philippine Normal University.
- Mendoza, M. (2012). Proficiency Level of Grade V and VI Multigrade Pupils in Reading, Barcelona Sorsogon: Unpublished Undergraduate Thesis. Sorsogon State College
- Nasrollahi M.A., Krishnasamy, P. N., & Noor, N. M. (2015). Identifying the critical reading strategies employed by Iranian EFL learners. *International J. Soc. Sci. & Education*, 5(2), 360-373.
- Orencia, Mary C. R. (2002). Enhancing Pupils Reading Comprehension and Attitudes Through a Whole Language-Inspired Literature-Based Reading Program. Philippine Normal University, Manila. Retrieved on 25 June 2018.
- Panerio, Reane O. (2008). Reading Comprehension Skills of Gubat South Central School. Unpublished Undergraduate Thesis: Bicol University Campus
- Philnews.ph. Philippines Lowest In Reading Comprehension Says Worldwide Study. December 4, 2019. <https://philnews.ph/2019/12/04/philippines-lowest-in-reading-comprehension-says-worldwide-study/>
- Ponitz, C., Rimm-Kaufman, S., Grimm, K., & Curby, T. (2009). Kindergarten classroom quality, behavioral engagement, and reading achievement. *School Psychology Review*, 38(1), 102-120.
- Simbulas, L. C., Regidor, B. T., & Catulpos, R. (2015). Reading comprehension and mathematical problem solving skills of university of the immaculate conception freshmen Students. *UIC Research Journal*, 21(2), 65-73. Retrieved January 27, 2019, from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=12835>
- Springer, (2011). *Reading Comprehension: Assisting Children with Learning Difficulties*. Woolley. Retrieved on 25 June 2018.
- Stipek, J.D. (2009). No child left behind comes to preschool. *Elementary School Journal*, (106), 455-465.
- Subibe, M. L. (2015). The effectiveness of using explicit skills instruction in improving the reading comprehension of struggling grade six pupils. *Jose Rizal University Journal of Business, Education and Law*, 20(1), 31-49. Retrieved November 29, 2018, from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=12240>

The Philippine Star, Friday, March 18, 2010. “How do Filipino students rate in reading?” <http://www.philstar.com/health-and-family/553720/how-do-filipino-students-rate-reading>

Tizon, M.N. 2013. Reading Comprehension Ability of Grade VI Pupils of Kinangay Sur Elementary School.

Uychoco, D. M. (2012). Academic Reading Proficiency of Freshmen in the College of Education of DMMMSU-SLUC: Input to the Design of Instructional Modules for English

Umaima , A.N. et al. (2018). Perceptions of Teachers about the Role of Parents in Developing Reading Habits of Children to Improve their Academic Performance in Schools. ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/IJERR/article/view/28592

Velasco, J. S., Ibabao, M., Sevilla, E., Jr., & Cayetano, J. (2016). Students’ reading attitudes: Improving the motivation of the freshman students of colegio de San Juan de Letran. *Luz Y Saber Scholarly Journal*, 1(2), 26-34. Retrieved January 4, 2019, from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=11453>

Vertucio, N. (2019). Reading Comprehension Skills in English of Grade 7 Students at San Nicolas National High School S.Y 2018-2019. <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/9140>

Yu, J. (2015). Analysis of critical reading strategies and its effect on college English reading. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 5(1), 134-138.

Zheng, P., and Libertus, M. (2018). The role of parental education, household income, and race on parents’ academic beliefs and the provision of home learning opportunities for 4- to 8-year-old children. *J. Educ. Dev. Psychol.* 8, 118–132. doi: 10.5539/jedp.v8n1p118

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Cloeyline P. Dela Rosa

Urdaneta City University – Philippines

Dr. Jeger P. Paragas

Umingan National High School

Department of Education – Philippines